

TIPS ON GETTING RECENT SCHOLARLY LITERATURE MATERIALS FOR THESIS AND OTHER ACADEMIC WRITING

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Abstract

It is now a prerequisite in many academic institutions and many academic journals that most of the cited works in academic writing, especially theses and dissertations, be recent. This short article aims to give some tips on how a researcher can get recent scholarly literature materials. The tips are based on the author's experience when he was writing his PhD thesis and thereafter. The article concluded with a recommendation that researchers should continue to explore the given tips and other means through modern technological tools to be up-to-date in their chosen fields.

Keywords: tips on recent scholarly works, Google Scholar, academic social network services, artificial intelligence (AI) tools, Sage Publications

Introduction

One of the requirements for writing a thesis at Lead City University (LCU), Ibadan, Nigeria is having a five-year recency of at least 75% of cited works in the thesis. A similar requirement is obtainable in other academic institutions. When this researcher started his Ph.D. study at LCU in 2019 and he was told this, he thought that it was impossible. However, he later discovered that it is possible with the help of some resources on the Internet. He could get more than enough recent scholarly works for his Ph.D. thesis and scaled through the hurdle of recency with ease at the Postgraduate College of the university. He is still enjoying these resources. So, the aim of this short article is to share some of the tips.

The Tips

1. Google Scholar Alert

This can be done by going to <https://www.google.com/alerts> and creating an alert for one's desired research interest. Input the email address you want these alerts to be sent. Google Scholar will be sending recently published materials, mostly scholarly literature, to you by email almost every day. This will continue to happen till you stop the alerts.

2. Google Scholar Customized Search

What is popular in searching for any information online is to search through normal Google or any other online search engine.¹ However, to get results from mostly scholarly materials, you have to use Google Scholar Search by visiting <https://www.scholar.google.com>. To get the most recent results, you can customize your search by specifying the range of years you desire by

¹ Adebayo Ola Afolaranmi (2009). *Ministering through the Internet: An Essential Guide*. (Ibadan: Charisa Books and Publishing), 53-54.

the left side of the opened Google Scholar Search window. Google Alerts can also be set through this service.

3. Using Academic Social Network Services

We are all familiar with many online social network services like Facebook, LinkedIn, and the like. There are some online social network services that are mainly for the academics. These online social network services are referred to as academic online social network services.² These services are specifically for scholars that have affiliation with academic and research institutes and “specialize in academic activities such as sharing studies, articles, and information.”³ Examples are <https://www.Academia.edu> and <https://www.Researchgate.net>. Others are Mendeley and Zotero who are becoming very popular among academics. You can join the networks and join other academics who share similar research interests with you. By indicating your research interests, these academic networks will be notifying you of recently published materials in your area of research interest by email. You can also use them to search for desired literature in your area of research interest.

4. Sage Publications

This is another academic online social network service that specializes in connecting researchers with academic journals that are associated with it. Its website is <https://journals.sagepub.com/>. You can find academic journals in almost every academic field on this network. You can join the network and indicate your research interest. You can also create alerts with some desired academic journals on the network, and you will receive alerts of newly published papers/articles in these journals by email.

5. Other Online Services

There are other online services that offer the services of providing information on recently published scholarly works. One of them is <https://www.emerald.com/>. Others are <https://www.connectedpapers.com/>, PubMed®, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>, and the like.

6. AI Tools

This researcher is aware of many recently launched artificial intelligence tools especially ChatGPT – an innovative technology that employs advanced artificial intelligence systems to create natural language answers to a given prompt or input.⁴ Others are <https://www.researchrabbit.ai/> and <https://elicit.org/> among others. This researcher has started studying these emerging technological tools. You may also explore them. However, this researcher will not advise any student to start using it for research purposes for now.

Conclusion

² M. Mohammad, Y. M. Lazim, & S. Rosle (2018). Academic Social Network Sites: Opportunities and Challenges. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(3.13), 133-134.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i3.13.16339>

³ H. Meishar-Tal & E. Pieterse (2017). Why Do Academics Use Academic Social Networking Sites? *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 18(1), 2. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1136066.pdf>

⁴ D. Kalla & N. Smith (2023). Study and Analysis of Chat GPT and its Impact on Different Fields of Study.

International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology, 8(3), March 2023.

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4402499

These aforementioned tips are not exhaustive. You can explore more online. They will not only help you in getting most recent scholarly publications during your thesis writing or any other academic writing, but also help you in your academic pursuits after your study. Therefore, it is recommended that researchers should continue to explore the given tips and other means through the modern technological tools to be up-to-date in their chosen fields.